

ONLINE VS IN PERSON: FLIPPED CLASSROOM APPROACHES TO A 3rd YEAR ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONIC ENGINEERING PROJECT MANAGEMENT MODULE

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ABSTRACT

Managing Engineering Projects is a 3rd Year module of the 4-year MEng in Electrical and Electronic Engineering with Management degree. Its purpose is to provide students with innovation and project management skills in the context of engineering practice.

The format was modified during the 2020-21 academic year to include more elements of student-centred learning to increase engagement given the online delivery format due to Covid. The module comprised 10 x 2-hour weekly sessions. Students were sent the material for each of the sessions ahead of time, with the first hour being devoted to discussing relevant aspects or issues raised by the students. The second hour focused on a related case study or activity, where students were allocated to break out rooms on Teams for group work, then coming together for some general discussion and conclusions. Alternatively, guest industrial speakers would share their professional experiences to illustrate the theory covered in the first hour. There was also an opportunity for questions and general project management discussion.

The module was delivered in person this academic year, retaining the same flipped classroom format, case studies and industrial speakers.

This paper compares the feedback and insights gathered through questionnaires from the online and in-person cohorts. Initial evidence shows that both groups found the flipped classroom, practical group work, and guest talks more engaging than traditional lectures. However, the in-person cohort showed higher rates of attendance and students were more engaged in group activities.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the module

The “Managing Engineering Projects” module was designed and taught for the first time in the spring term (January to March) of 2019. It is offered to 3rd Year students on the Management Stream of our MEng Electrical and Electronic course.

The module comprised 10x2-hour sessions with 1 hour of traditional lecturing, or passive learning, and 1 hour where an industrial speaker would illustrate the material covered in the lecture, or the cohort would work in groups on a case study or management challenges.

The format was modified during the spring term 2021 to include more elements of student-centred learning [1] to increase engagement, given the online delivery format due to Covid. Using a flipped classroom, students were sent the material for each of the topics ahead of time, with the first hour being devoted to discussing relevant aspects or issues raised by the students. The second hour remained unchanged.

The module was delivered in person this spring term, retaining the same flipped classroom format, case studies and industrial speakers [2].

This paper compares the feedback and insights gathered via questionnaires as well as levels of engagement from the online (Group 1) and in-person (Group 2) cohorts.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Student sample details

Two groups were sampled for this paper; Group 1 who experienced the module through online delivery in 2021 and Group 2 who attended face to face in 2022.

Table 1. Details of student sample

Group	Cohort	Delivery method	Cohort size	Attendance and engagement
1	2021	Online	49	69.39%
2	2022	In person	17	88.23%

2.2 Questionnaires

Both cohorts of students were asked to complete a 16-question questionnaire (see Appendix) anonymously. Only Questions 3 and 4 were considered for this paper.

Table 2. Questions 3 and 4

Q3. Class format - which format do you find most suitable for the way in which you learn?
Q4. Class format- please explain the rationale for your selection in Q3

2.2.1 Question 3

The purpose of Q3 was to establish which learning format was best suited to the respondent’s learning style. The responses included the options available in pre-Covid

times (face to face, online pre-recorded and live discussions, a combination) and the most widely approach applied during Covid and the various lockdowns: online live. Respondents also had the opportunity to add their own method under the “Other” reply.

2.2.2 Question 4

Q4 was free text to allow respondents to elaborate on their answers for Q3. These replies gave great insights into their attitude and motivation towards learning in the context of the pandemic.

2.2.3 Level of engagement

The level of engagement was obtained by calculating the number of students who attended more than 50% of the classes as a proportion of the total number of students. This threshold was selected as it is the minimum number of sessions students can attend and still have the knowledge necessary to successfully complete the coursework.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Question 3

Group 1 showed a clear preference for traditional lectures (46.1%) while Group 2 was equally divided amongst flipped classroom, traditional lectures, and a combination of both. The percentage for flipped classroom, however, remained almost constant, moving from 30.8% to 33.3%.

Fig 1: Q3 results for Groups 1 and 2

3.1.2 Question 4

Group 1 provided feedback with opinions on both passive and active learning camps:

“If the course consists of only traditional lectures, it can be boring, and I switch off. However, sometimes, it is useful to have the material explained by the lecturer”

“I like to view the content first and then have time to do further research after.”

“I would maintain an element of pre-lecture preparation through case study readings”

Group 2 were more in favour of active learning, as the results show:

“This [flipped classroom] would help us gain information and exchange ideas more effectively for learning.”

“It’s more interactive which is also suits the nature of the content being delivered”

“The pre-recorded videos are useful for learning new information as everyone learns at a different pace. However online discussions don’t have good participation and should be face to face”

Fig 2: Group 2 students applying material from flipped classroom to a case study

3.1.3 Level of engagement

The results are quite disparate, with Group 1 scoring 69.39% and Group 2 88.23%. The reasons for this difference have been included the Discussion section.

3.2 Discussion

Group 1 were in the last term of their 2nd year during the first lockdown in March 2020, and had to adapt to online learning, exams, presentations, and assessments very quickly. Unfortunately, most of the following academic year was delivered online as well, resulting in students spending many hours in front of their screens listening to traditional lectures [3]. The level of uncertainty at the time meant that many academics made only slight changes to the material and the delivery since there was the expectation of a return to normal by October 2021.

After 2 terms of online learning, students attended online classes live but switched off their cameras, to do something unrelated while the class was on in the background. Other students took a “binge watching” approach to their learning by missing live sessions and then watching several sessions, one after the other.

This “screen fatigue” and the requirement to prepare material ahead of the class explain the level of engagement for this cohort being 69.39% vs 83.23% for Group 2.

Group 2 on the other hand, were in Year 1 when lockdown started and completed Year 2, the most demanding in the course, online. They had missed the social aspect of learning and were keen to return to campus and face to face teaching. Hence the important level of engagement.

There was consensus in the value of and appreciation for the industrial speakers, as they gave insights into potential career paths.

In conclusion, two separate cohorts enrolled on the same module had quite different experiences: online and face to face. Group 1 was less interested in a flipped-classroom approach since it involved preparatory work and online discussions, which students find intimidating. Group 2, in contrast, was more interested in active learning as the discussions were face to face and more productive.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

Q1. Course delivery - which format do you find most suitable for the way which you learn?

Q2. Course delivery - please explain the rationale for your selection in Q1

Q3. Class format - which format do you find most suitable for the way in which you learn?

Q4. Class format- please explain the rationale for your selection in Q3

Q5. How did you find working on practical examples, case studies and group discussions? For example, deployment of Covid vaccine to remote locations, organising Hackathon, Europa Foods, etc.

Q6. Guest industrial speakers - what is your opinion?

Q7. Industrial speakers - what would you keep and why?

Q8. Industrial speakers - what would you change and why? what alternatives would you propose?

Q9. Assessment - cw1 essay on a project management topic

Q10. Assessment cw1- what would you keep and why?

Q11. Assessment cw 1 - what would you change and why? what alternatives would you propose?

Q12. Assessment - cw2 "Turning your 2nd Year EERover into an educational toy" group project

Q13. Cw2 deliverables - group project (Video and Q&A session)

Q14. Cw2 deliverables - group project deliverables (Report)

Q15. Assessment cw2- what would you keep and why?

Q16. Assessment cw 2- what would you change and why? what alternatives would you propose?